

IMPROVING THE USE OF MARKETING STRATEGIES OF
ENTERPRISES IN SOCIAL NETWORKS

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the importance of marketing strategies of enterprises in social networks, their creation and development, ways to improve their use. Content in social media is created by users themselves for other users, providing the opportunity to find friends, exchange photos, audio and video information, and unite by interests.*

Keywords. *Marketing, marketing strategies, social networks, contents, social media, audio, video, information, consumer.*

Over the past few years, there has been a growing trend in the popularity of social networks as a means of promoting a company and its products. This is primarily due to such advantages of social media as relatively low cost (in some cases, promotion can be completely free), wide coverage of the target audience, flexibility, the possibility of targeting (orientation of advertising to a clearly focused group based on various characteristics), ease of launching a project for promotion, the ability to quickly make changes. In addition, content in social media is created by users themselves for other users, providing the opportunity to find friends, exchange photos, audio and video information, and unite by interests. Social networks also allow for a high level of personalization of appeals.

Despite the popularity of social media and their widespread use in marketing activities, it is necessary to identify the main mistakes that companies make when implementing marketing communications in networks, as well as highlight the main strategic alternatives to their use.

There are several reasons why a company might use social media to implement an online marketing communications strategy:

1. Organization of communications between employees or various departments of the company, both with the aim of forming a corporate spirit and a favorable attitude towards the company, and for holding meetings and discussions, regardless of the location of the employee.

2. Reducing communication costs for any area of business, regardless of the size of the company.

3. Searching and attracting employees, creating the image of a “preferred place of work”; searching for information about candidates for vacant positions.

4. Using social media to reach end consumers to increase sales, implement communication goals and create a certain image of the company, further support and service (i.e. implementation of support service functions).

5. Identifying consumer attitudes towards the brand.

6. Increasing the degree of customer loyalty to the brand.

7. Attracting additional traffic to the company’s website.

8. Business expansion, company growth.

The main advantages of using social networks, in our opinion, include:

- ✓ simplicity and ease of disseminating information (you can create a group on the Internet faster than the simplest business card website);

- ✓ absence of spatial restrictions;

- ✓ responsiveness;

- ✓ voluntary communication;

- ✓ ease of maintaining feedback with consumers;

- ✓ the possibility of saving financial resources;
- ✓ short terms for launching an advertising campaign;
- ✓ clear identification of the target audience, since a social network is a resource that independently actively attracts users;
- ✓ the possibility of using viral marketing tools, since joining a group usually has an impulsive chain nature;
- ✓ interactivity.

However, like any marketing tool, social networks are not without drawbacks, among which the first place is occupied by the “multiple social network syndrome”, which forces users to register and maintain contacts in several resources at once, as well as view a large number of notifications. In addition, any user, including representatives of a commercial company who organize a group on social networks to promote products, will encounter difficulties if the need arises to delete a page (group).

Disadvantages also include a poorly developed mobile interface and the possibility of virus infection. As in the case of maintaining a corporate blog, working on a social network requires a significant investment of time while reducing financial costs.

The need to allocate a specialist who spends the bulk of his working time implementing marketing communications online also seems to be one of the disadvantages of social media. In the social environment, as a rule, there is an uncontrolled dissemination of information, there is no guarantee of preservation and protection of information, and there is a danger of disclosure of confidential information. Often, these shortcomings lead to unpredictability of the results of a company’s presence on social networks.

One of the characteristic features of social networks that allows them to be used effectively for marketing purposes is their wide audience coverage. More than

15 million Uzbek Internet users visit at least one social network per month, which accounts for more than 75% of all Uzbek Internet users.

Most impulse purchases are made on social networks. Thus, the most suitable for promotion on social networks are:

- inexpensive entertainment products (as opposed to functional and practical products);
- symbolic goods that are used to create or strengthen individuality and image (branded and fashion items, luxury items, jewelry, sports and club goods, music, etc.);
- “instant gratification” goods, the pleasure from which can be obtained immediately (digital products).

Social media is becoming an increasingly popular marketing tool, which is primarily due to the active growth in the number of registered users and the increase in time spent online. However, despite the active growth, not all Uzbek companies competently use this marketing tool, on the one hand, underestimating its capabilities, on the other hand, expecting instant returns without wasting human and time resources.

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